

Strategy for the adoption and use of an AAI within ELIXIR

Agreed on by the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes 14 June 2016

Executive summary

ELIXIR aims to provide a sustainable, user-friendly Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) to meet the evolving needs of all life scientists in Europe.

It will achieve this aim by:

- 1) Continuing to deploy a forwards-compatible, sustainable AAI within ELIXIR.
- 2) Consulting and collaborating with other biological and medical sciences (BMS) research infrastructures and other key life sciences initiatives to ensure interoperability and harmonisation.
- 3) Collaborating and partnering with GEANT and other e-Infrastructures to realise the vision of a Europe-wide AAI service which is common with other research infrastructures and based on federated identity management.

Purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to canvas an internal agreement in ELIXIR, and to consult with the key external stakeholders, on ELIXIR's requirements and expectations for shared, distributed user authentication and resource authorisation services.

This document is to be prepared within the ELIXIR compute platform and technical coordinators. As the second step, it is sent to the e-infrastructures for consultation. Finally, the document intends to be presented to HoN meeting in 14-15 June 2016 for agreement.

Background

Authentication is the process of verifying the identity of the person who is trying to log in. Authentication has a given degree of certainty over how robust the identification process is

(known as Level of Assurance). *Authorisation* is the process of giving a person access and permissions within a given service.

During the last decade in the research and education sector, the trend has been to limit the number of credentials (such as usernames and passwords) a user (a researcher) needs. Ideally, the user would just have the credentials their home institution (the institution's IT services) provides them, and the e-infrastructures (such as GEANT) would enable them to use these credentials in any service in a secure way. This approach is called federated identity management.

During 2014-2015, the ELIXIR AAI task force gathered use cases and requirements for an AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) that offers ELIXIR the services for authentication and authorisation of end users. EXCELERATE¹ WP4 started to deploy the ELIXIR AAI in September 2015. The ELIXIR community is also discussing AAI with other research infrastructures and e-infrastructures in various forums, such as CORBEL² WP5, the AARC³ project and the FIM4R⁴ community.

Vision of the AAI

ELIXIR aims to provide a sustainable, user-friendly Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) to meet the evolving needs of all life scientists in Europe.

User-friendly means

- The user has a single set or a small number of credentials with different Levels of Assurance that they can use to log in to ELIXIR services,
- When possible, the users are able to have a single sign-on experience, i.e. they need to present their credentials only in the beginning of the session,
- The users are able to use web-based tools to apply for additional access rights and the lead time to receive them is minimised.

Stakeholder analysis

The ELIXIR Compute platform oversees the ELIXIR technical infrastructure, including the AAI. It is the body that ensures the AAI interoperates with other technical infrastructures (such as data and cloud) and together provides a service that meets the needs of ELIXIR.

¹ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/excelerate>

² <http://www.corbel-project.eu/>

³ <https://aarc-project.eu/>

⁴ <https://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/1442597/files/CERN-OPEN-2012-006.pdf>

Scientific use cases (EXCELERATE WP 6-9) and the ELIXIR training platform are the frontline customers of the ELIXIR AAI. Within the EXCELERATE project, ELIXIR AAI's success is measured by its ability to serve their needs.

CORBEL WP5 is the CORBEL project work package focusing on enabling common solutions for user access. It is the forum for AAI collaboration within the BMS research infrastructures.

e-infrastructures (such as GEANT⁵ or EGI⁶) provide AAI services (such as the eduGAIN inter-federation service) and tools that ELIXIR AAI builds on. e-infrastructure projects also provide a community where ELIXIR has an opportunity to meet and discuss with other research infrastructures the AAI needs and solutions (e.g. through participation in the AARC project or the EGI ENGAGE Competence Centres).

ELIXIR AAI service position

It is anticipated that the ELIXIR AAI services will become an essential building block for many other ELIXIR services. It is necessary to ensure the continuity of the AAI service, regardless of who is actually managing (operating) its components.

Therefore the ELIXIR AAI is defined as a service that falls under the responsibility of the ELIXIR Hub. This enables ELIXIR to commission AAI services from Nodes ("Commissioned Service" as defined in the ELIXIR Consortium Agreement⁷) or obtain them from e-infrastructures and re-organise the service as the circumstances change over time. The capabilities of the AAI service will be specified by the Hub, following the community input.

External relations

Relations to e-infrastructures

ELIXIR supports and leverages the AAI services provided by e-infrastructures, including the eduGAIN inter-federation service of GEANT. ELIXIR has an interest to ensure eduGAIN is further developed in a way that supports ELIXIR. This covers a seamless service, level of assurance and well-defined semantics of user data irrespective to which country the user comes from.

⁵ <http://www.geant.org/>

⁶ <http://www.egi.eu/>

⁷ According to the ELIXIR Consortium Agreement, the ELIXIR Board may commission technical or administrative services from the Node that would normally fall under the responsibility of the Hub.

Running its own AAI is not a core competence for ELIXIR. In the long run, ELIXIR intends to rely upon e-infrastructure partners, such as GEANT⁸ or EGI, in the operations of the ELIXIR AAI or some of its components. ELIXIR's long term vision is that ELIXIR AAI services are subsumed and form a part of (for example) GEANT provided, pan-European AAI services. A core part of our strategy is to closely collaborate with GEANT and other e-infrastructures to realise this vision.

ELIXIR AAI should also support both strong identity verification and reliable (strong) authentication of researchers. To cover these requirements, ELIXIR closely follows the development of government-owned citizen-ID systems (c.f. the eIDAS regulation⁹ or STORK activities) or similar GEANT and other e-infrastructures research activities and follow up services.

Relations to other BMS research infrastructures and communities

ELIXIR supports creation of a common interoperable AAI for life science researchers. This would enable an end user to use a single identity (credentials) to access the services they are permitted to access in all BMS research infrastructures.

ELIXIR works with other BMS research infrastructures in CORBEL WP5, the ongoing AARC and the proposed AARC2 projects to achieve this vision. Meanwhile, ELIXIR continues deploying its own AAI services within EXCELERATE, with the intention to ensure they will become compatible with the common AAI when it emerges.

ELIXIR continues the dialogue with international communities like Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) regarding common architectures and access models. ELIXIR contributes to and, where possible, adopts compatible concepts for access management (such as, the concept and definition of a "bona fide researcher").

ELIXIR authentication and authorisation reference model

This section introduces a layered reference model for authentication and authorisation in ELIXIR services. It is up to each service relying on ELIXIR AAI ("Relying Service") to decide to which layer their service belongs.

⁸ GEANT Virtual Organisation Platform as a service. Market analysis.

http://www.geant.org/Projects/GEANT_Project_GN4-1/deliverables/D9-2_Market-Analysis-for-Virtual-Organisation-Platform-as-a-Service.pdf

⁹ Assurance levels for electronic identification means pursuant to eIDAS regulation.

http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2015.235.01.0007.01.ENG

Authentication layers

The ELIXIR AAI provides an authentication framework with three different Levels of Assurance.

1. *Basic*. There is minimal confidence in the claimed or asserted identity of the user, but some confidence that the user is the same over consecutive authentication events. A user can self-register and self-assert their identity. No shared accounts are expected. The following external authentication providers fall into this layer:
 - a. Common external identity providers such as Google, LinkedIn and ORCID.
 - b. eduGAIN identity providers who do not attain the proposed Minimum LoA level¹⁰ definition of the e-infrastructures.
2. *Raised*. There is some confidence in the claimed or asserted identity of the User.
 - a. eduGAIN Identity Providers that support at least the Minimum LoA level definition proposed in the e-infrastructures.
3. *Strong*. There is high confidence in the claimed or asserted identity of the user. Reliable registration of new users (identity proofing) and a strong authentication (based on two authentication factors).
 - a. eIDAS assurance levels substantial and high.

The Compute platform will define the requirements of the layers in detail.

Authorisation layers

The ELIXIR AAI provides the following approaches for the Relying Parties to manage access rights to their service:

1. *Fully public*. The service does not need any authorisation; anyone can use it (the service may still need authentication if a user has a profile in the service).
2. *Registered*. The service requires that the user has a specific status or/and another attribute (e.g. “bona fide researcher”, membership in a group).
3. *Controlled*. The user needs to make a request which requires approval from the individual or body responsible for the service in question. For instance, a Data Access Committee that manages permissions to access a sensitive human dataset may require a research outline to be submitted.

The Compute platform will define the properties and functionalities of the layers in detail.

Eligibility to use the ELIXIR AAI

Any natural person, including researchers working for the industry, can become an ELIXIR end user by registering an ELIXIR identity.

¹⁰ Recommendations on minimal assurance level relevant for low-risk research use cases: <https://aarc-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/MNA31-Minimum-LoA-level.pdf>

The following organisations can become Relying Parties for ELIXIR AAI and register a service (Relying Service) that consumes the authentication and authorisation services ELIXIR AAI provides:

- The ELIXIR Nodes and the Hub
- Other public and private organisations based on an approval by the HoN Committee and the ELIXIR Director. The HoN Committee and ELIXIR Director can delegate their approval rights.

The Relying Services registered by Relying Parties must support research and collaboration in life sciences.

Policies and requirements for end users, Relying Parties and AAI operators

The ELIXIR AAI has the following policies for the parties involved:

- **Acceptable usage policy**, which specifies the terms to which any end user registering an ELIXIR Identity must commit to.
- **Policy for Relying Parties**, which a party relying on ELIXIR AAI must commit to.
- **Requirements for ELIXIR AAI operators**, which a party operating the technical components of ELIXIR AAI must commit to.

As long as ELIXIR AAI is a service provided by a Node, it is up to the Node to determine the AAI policies and incorporate them in its Service Delivery Plan. The draft ELIXIR AAI policies are in Appendix A-C.

Appendix A: Acceptable Usage Policy

About this document

This document forms the Acceptable Usage Policy of ELIXIR AAI, i.e. the terms to which any end user registering an ELIXIR Identity must commit to. The end user expresses their commitment to these terms at the time they log in to ELIXIR AAI for the first time, and their commitment to these terms are logged for audit trail.

Relation to other policies

This Acceptable Usage Policy forms the policy foundation for end users using ELIXIR services.

Individual ELIXIR services may have additional rules and policies which complement this document. For instance, access to sensitive human data may require the end user to commit to a data access agreement.

Acceptable Use Policy and Conditions of Use

By registering as a user you declare that you have read, understood and will abide by the following conditions of use¹¹:

1. You shall only use the resources/services to your professional activities related to the development and use of services for life science research.
2. You shall provide appropriate acknowledgement of support or citation for your use of the resources/services provided as required by the service you access.
3. You shall not use the resources/services for any purpose that is unlawful and not (attempt to) breach or circumvent any administrative or security controls.
4. You shall respect intellectual property and confidentiality agreements.
5. You shall protect your access credentials (e.g. private keys or passwords) and not share your account or credentials with anyone.
6. You shall keep all your registered information correct and up to date.
7. You shall immediately report any known or suspected security breach or misuse of the resources/services or access credentials to the specified incident reporting locations.
8. You use the resources/services at your own risk. There is no guarantee that the resources/services will be available at any time or that their integrity or confidentiality will be preserved or that they will suit any purpose.
9. You agree that logged information, including personal data provided by you for registration purposes, may be used for administrative, operational, accounting, monitoring and security purposes. You agree that this logged information may be

¹¹ Based on the Acceptable Usage Policy of EGI, March 2015.

disclosed to other authorised participants via secured mechanisms, only for the same purposes and only as far as necessary to provide the services.

10. You agree that ELIXIR and resource/service providers are entitled to regulate, suspend or terminate your access without prior notice and without compensation, within their domain of authority, and you shall immediately comply with their instructions.
11. You are liable for the consequences of your violation of any of these conditions of use, which may include but are not limited to the reporting of your violation to your home institute and, if the activities are thought to be illegal, to appropriate law enforcement agencies.

Appendix B: Policy for Relying Parties

About this document

This document forms the contractual terms to which a Relying Party of the ELIXIR AAI must commit to.

Terms in this document

A Relying Service means a service provided by a Relying Party that relies on the identity, authentication and/or authorisation services provided by ELIXIR AAI.

A Relying Party means an organisation managing one or more Relying Service(s), either itself or through an agent (such as a contractor) that manages the service on behalf of the Relying Party.

Policy for Relying Parties

Protection of ELIXIR End Users' personal data

- The Relying Party must follow laws, especially the data protection laws applicable in the country where the Relying Service is established, with regards to the End User's personal data it receives from the ELIXIR AAI.
- To receive restricted user attributes, such as those retrieved from the user's Home Organisation, the Relying Party must commit to GEANT Data protection Code of Conduct, version 1.0¹² or equivalent.
- If the Relying Party is outside EU/EEA and the countries with adequate protection of personal data the Relying Party must take measures deemed appropriate by the European Commission, such as, to commit to the Contractual Clauses¹³.

Liability

- The liability between an ELIXIR Node and the Hub is defined in the section 12 of the ELIXIR Collaboration Agreement.

¹² <https://wiki.refeds.org/display/CODE/Code+of+Conduct+for+Service+Providers>

¹³ http://ec.europa.eu/justice/data-protection/international-transfers/transfer/index_en.htm

Appendix C: Requirements for ELIXIR AAI operators

About this document

This document presents what the ELIXIR community expects from the organisations operating the ELIXIR AAI components.

Requirements for ELIXIR AAI operators

Security and availability:

- The security of the AAI services is taken care of professionally.
- The AAI operations are provided on a best effort basis. Normally, the AAI services are expected to be available 24/7. The ELIXIR Hub will monitor the availability of the services.

Purpose of processing personal data:

- The operator must process the ELIXIR end users' personal data only for what is necessary for the operations of the AAI.
- The operator is responsible that any necessary personal data processing is done in accordance to the applicable laws.
- The log files produced by the AAI components must be used only for administrative, operational, accounting, monitoring and security purposes.

Statistics:

- The operator aggregates and provides statistics about the consumption and use of the AAI services. The statistics must not reveal the identity of the users and the exact resources (such as the datasets) used.